

CREATION OF MEDIA TEXT IN NEWS PROGRAMS AND ITS FEATURES

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Abstract. *This thesis examines specific aspects of creating media texts in the information society.*

The main goal of this dissertation is to classify the possibilities of media texts in the media, analyze what should be paid attention to when using them effectively, and present scientific proposals. This research draws on a wide range of insights from media studies, linguistics, and psycholinguistics, making it a comprehensive interdisciplinary study.

Keywords: mass media, addressee factor, primary semantic writing, editing, media text, compositional-linguistic plan, genre, intertextuality, semiotics.

Introduction

Recently, the “effect of influence” has been most thoroughly and consistently realized in media discourse (Maurer P. and Arendt F., 2016). This process is especially clearly reflected in media products. This is directly related to media texts

that ensure the effectiveness of media products. New Zealand sociolinguist Allan Bell writes: “The term media text has gone beyond the traditional idea of a text as a sequence of words printed or written on paper. The concept of a media text is comprehensive and includes vocal features, music and sound effects, and visual representations.” (Bell Allan, 1996)

Methods and Results

When creating a media text, the author must answer such questions by using “what?” “what about?” “how?” “to whom?” “why?” (Maidanova L. and Kalganova S., 2006)

Considering the rules of modern text theory and psycholinguistics, creating a text, mainly a television media text, includes several stages.

The first stage. Some information is an impetus, a motivating reason for creating a media text. Understanding it, the writer decides what (information) and what (news) he wants to say; that is, he creates an idea of an opinion. Some linguists call this stage “primary semantic writing.” At this moment, the future text's general meaning is determined. Although it is possible to edit an idea during the work process, a certain number of ideas and facts are necessary for the initial stage of creativity. The ratio of information and news (topics and opinions, what to talk about, and what to say) creates the semantic basis of the future message and ensures its content consistency (Luria A., 1979).

At the next stage, the process of consistent formation, clear expression of thoughts, and reflection on the content of the text takes place. It is at this stage that the author must take into account the 'addressee factor' and decide who and what the text is intended for and how his relationship with the addressee will be established. This consideration of the audience's perspective is crucial, as it ensures that the text is not only well-crafted but also resonates with its readers, making them feel considered and valued in the communication process.

According to psycholinguists, the “spiritual” program of reasoning created at this stage includes answers to questions such as “what to say, in what order, and how to say it,” revealing the original “idea.”

The third stage is the polishing of the language of the text. At this stage, the compositional and linguistic plan of the work is determined. Since a written text is in a logical sequence, the author decides where to start, in what sequence, according to what logical laws to present the information, and how to finish the text. It should be noted that most news programs are first created as written text, and only after editing are they voiced and edited. Of course, genre features are also considered when composing a text. Depending on the genre of the information being prepared, its requirements may change.

Genres in journalism are not just formal categories, but they also serve as a 'technological necessity' that guides the practical activity of text creation. Each genre has its unique form and specific content, and the characters within the genre develop relationships. The structure of the genre exhibits both stability and variability, reflecting the dynamic nature of journalism (Kurban Nazira, 2020).

Russian professor Lyudmila Mайданова, PhD in Philology, and Svetlana Kalganova, PhD in Philology, associate professor, say that genres can be classified depending on the "technical methods" used to construct the text. According to their interpretation, it is divided into five groups:

- Genres for “recording evidence”: news, articles, and reports.
- Genres for “analysis of evidence”: article, analytical report, analytical report, review, observation, survey.
- Genres for “writing a text about a text”: review, “educational story,” magazine, and other radio interpretation.
- Genres for “writing a dialogic text”: various interviews, talk shows, the new “Open Communication” genre, and press conferences.

• Genres for “creating an image of a form of speech”: essay, film, feuilleton, essay.”

Consulition

So, in consulition “a media text is a text created with the help of media materials and tools.” For this reason, in the modern global information age, not using modern media tools when creating a text is tantamount to missing the opportunity to attract an audience.

It is essential to find a topic that can interest the audience, correctly choose the topic of the media text, and present it according to the requirements of the time without deviating from the rules of journalism.

REFERENCES:

Bell Allan. (1996). *Approaches to Media Discourse*. London: Blackwell.

Kurban Nazira. (2020). *Analytical journalism*. Tashkent: Uzkitobsavdonashriyoli.

Luria A. (1979). *Language and consciousness*. Moscow : Publishing House Moscow.

Maidanova L. and Kalganova S. (2006). *Practical stylistics of media genres*. Ekaterinburg: Humanitarian University.

Maurer P. and Arendt F. (2016). A blessing or a double-edged sword? Politicians’ perceptions of newspapers’ impact on the functioning of democracy. *Communications*, 41(1), PP. 1-20. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1515/commun-2015-0027>

YANGILIK DASTURLARIDA MEDIAMATNNI YARATISH VA UNING XUSUSIYATLARI

Munira Nazarova Yusupovna

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu tezis axborot jamiyatida media matnlarni yaratishning o'ziga xos jihatlarini ko'rib chiqadi.*

Ushbu bitiruv malakaviy ishining asosiy maqsadi OAVdagi mediamatnlarning imkoniyatlarini tasniflash, ulardan unumli foydalanishda nimalarga e'tibor qaratish lozimligini tahlil qilish va ilmiy takliflar berishdan iborat. Ushbu tadqiqot media tadqiqotlari, tilshunoslik va psixolingvistikadan keng ko'lamli tushunchalarga asoslanib, uni keng qamrovli fanlararo tadqiqotga aylantiradi.

Kalit so'zlar: ommaviy axborot vositalari, adresat omili, birlamchi semantik yozuv, tahrir, media matn, kompozitsion-lingvistik reja, janr, intertekstuallik, semiotika.